
Progress: 0%

Thank you for your interest in this survey "problems of newcomers in development teams in the area of communication".

This survey addresses persons who do or will work in software development teams.

In this survey we want to examine which problems newcomers in development teams face, especially in the area of communication. This is why it is interesting to gather real experiences as well as ideas of people with no experience so far. You can therefore participate in this survey if you have experience as a developer, but also if not.

Please state which one is true for you.

All answers will be collected and treated anonymously. The collected data will be handled strictly confidential. Therefore, please do not add personal details in the open-ended fields. The collected data in aggregated form will probably be used in publications. If you proceed with this survey, you agree to these terms.

If you have any questions about this survey, please contact anonymus@anonymus.com.

Please note that on some mobile devices some questions might not be displayed correctly. Please use a device with a larger screen to fill out the survey.

Do you have work experience in the area of software development? Occupations as a working student or intern also count.

Yes

No

Please think about the last time you joined a new team. In the following survey, all questions refer to this specific situation.

Please try to remember this specific situation and briefly describe it.

How many employees did the company have (approximately)?

- 10 or less
- 11-50
- 51-250
- 251 or more

How many developers were in your team, in addition to you (approximately)?

In how many companies have you worked before?

- 0
- 1
- 2-5
- 6 or more

How many times did you join a new team in total?

We would like to learn more about the communication in your team. Your team probably used different communication channels.

Communication channels are options to communicate via message or text with one or more colleagues. There are active communication channels, where both sides actively communicate (e.g. e-mail or chat), and passive communication channels, where a single person provides information to others (e.g. wiki or poster).

In this survey we are looking into written communication channels. Phone calls or personal meetings are therefore explicitly excluded.

Please select which channels have been used in your team.

- Personal e-mail
- Mailing List

- Chat (e.g. Slack, Gitter, IRC, Mattermost, ...)
- Forum
- Social Media (e.g. Facebook, Twitter, ...)
- Issue Tracker (e.g. GitLab Issues, Jira, ...)
- Wiki (e.g. Confluence, ...)
- Intranet with chat or documentation function (e.g. Sharepoint)
- Call Tool with chat function (e.g. Skype)
- Physical Notes (e.g. Flipchart, Kanban Board, ...)
- Other Physical Announcements (e.g. posters, instructions, ...)
- Other
- Other

How often were the channels used?

	Daily	Several times a week	Several times a month	Once a month	Less	Never
Personal e-mail	<input type="radio"/>					
Mailing List	<input type="radio"/>					
Chat (e.g. Slack, Gitter, IRC, Mattermost, ...)	<input type="radio"/>					
Forum	<input type="radio"/>					
Social Media (e.g. Facebook, Twitter, ...)	<input type="radio"/>					
Issue Tracker (e.g. GitLab Issues, Jira, ...)	<input type="radio"/>					
Wiki (e.g. Confluence, ...)	<input type="radio"/>					
Intranet with chat or documentation function (e.g. Sharepoint)	<input type="radio"/>					
Call Tool with chat function (e.g. Skype)	<input type="radio"/>					
Physical Notes (e.g. Flipchart, Kanban Board, ...)	<input type="radio"/>					
Other Physical Announcements (e.g. posters, instructions, ...)	<input type="radio"/>					
Other <input type="text"/>	<input type="radio"/>					
Other <input type="text"/>	<input type="radio"/>					

How many individual channels were used in total? Please do not count the categories but the single channels.

For example, if Slack and Mattermost were used as a chat, you can count two channels.

**In some companies there are rules for communication channels. They state (officially or unofficially) which topics should be communicated in which channels.
Were there such rules in your team?**

- Yes, for all channels
- Yes, for some channels
- No
- Don't know

**Please give an example for such a rule.
If there were no rules, please imagine an appropriate rule.**

Which principles did you follow to use which channel? How did you decide which channel to use for which message? Did you follow the rules?

Now we would like to know if there were any problems when using the communication channels after your start.

Especially, we would like to know if the following problems occurred:

- I could not find messages/information again.
- Messages were gone (e.g. deleted, or the chat history did not go that far).
- Only messages written after my channel entrance were visible.
- Information was distributed over multiple channels.

- Information was only documented in a message and not in the official documentation.
- Information was outdated.
- I was not sure where to share which information.
- It was time-consuming to find information on a topic.
- None of the above
- Other

Please describe any other problems which occurred in the area of communication.

Please assess whether the problems have occurred more or less often since you have joined the team.

	Occurs (nearly) always	Occurs more often	Occurs equally often	Occurs less often	Does not occur anymore
I cannot find messages/information again.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Messages are gone (e.g. deleted, or the chat history did not go that far).	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Only messages written after my channel entrance are visible.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Information is distributed over multiple channels.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Information is only documented in a message and not in the official documentation.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Information is outdated.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I am not sure where to share which information.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
It is time-consuming to find information on a topic.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
None of the above	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other <input type="text"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Finally, we have some questions for statistical purposes.

How old are you?

How old were you during the scenario you thought of?

What is your gender?

- Male
- Female
- Diverse
- Don't want to answer

Thank you for your participation. Your answers are very important to us.

Do you have any comments?

Continue